

Optimization of 3D Printing Process Parameters for Improving the Mechanical Behavior of Honeycomb-Core Sandwich Panels

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Abstract: The emergence of additive manufacturing has enabled the production of complex functional objects, including biomimetic structures, to be produced more easily. The purpose of this study is to enhance the mechanical behavior of honeycomb-core sandwich panels, produced using the FFF process, by optimizing the level setting of printing parameters, and to evaluate the significant impact of the printing parameters. To determine the optimal parameter level and assess the significant impact of the parameters, the Taguchi method and ANOVA were utilized. The findings indicated that the optimal values of the parameters for either compressive strength or bending strength were 230°C nozzle temperature, 0.1 mm layer height, 20 mm/s print speed, and 40°C platform temperature. Statistically, all the printing parameters used have significant impact on the flexural strength of the honeycomb-core sandwich panels, while only platform temperature has an insignificant effect on the compressive strength. Finally, the highest compressive and flexural strength attained are 1.88 MPa and 9.4 MPa, respectively. This finding in general had higher values of mechanical properties of the honeycomb-core sandwich panel compared to the previous studies which utilized similar dimensional specifications and specimen sizes.

Keywords: biomimetics; fused filament fabrication (FFF); honeycomb structure; mechanical behavior; Taguchi method

1. Introduction

In recent years, biomimetics have attracted a lot of interest and acknowledgment as a science that imitates and applies the principles observed in nature to address engineering challenges. For the creation of novel materials and structures, this method has shown to be an excellent source of inspiration. Over millions of years, species in nature evolved intricate structures that offer strength, efficiency, and adaptability. Researchers and engineers developed bio-inspired materials and structures that emulate the beneficial aspects of the environment by examining and comprehending these natural structures¹.

Past research has been conducted to identify the types of biomimetic structures used in various applications. For example, honeycomb structures²⁻¹² and bamboo structures^{13,14} have been applied as robust design structure and energy absorption; bone structure¹⁵⁻¹⁷ have been utilized for cancellous bone tissue engineering and femur bone-implant scaffold; horse hoof structure^{18,19} have been studied to improve the impact strength and structural

stability of the material; the elements of water droplets and snowflakes²⁰ have been explored to increase the internal structural resistance of the parts of the turbine system (such as the gas and hydroelectric turbine blades, OGVs, nacelles, gearboxes); fish scale arrays, crocodile, and armadillo scales^{21,22} have been used for flexible natural armors; microstructure²³ have been developed for bone scaffolds; mantis shrimp shell structures²⁴ have been explored for dental restoration; chiton scale structure²⁵ have been applied in military and sports protective clothing design; Bouligand structures in American lobster²⁶ have been adopted to enhance fracture deflection and energy absorption; and beetle's front wing structures²⁷ have been utilized in lattice structures. All the structures mentioned above are inspired by nature.

The honeycomb, commonly found in bee colonies, is a widely recognized bio-inspired structure that has been extensively developed and utilized. Its design is highly effective for load-bearing applications, as its individual cells shape up hexagonally, establishing the ideal balance between weight and toughness¹. Because of its high ratio

of stiffness to weight and strength to weight, honeycomb is particularly effective as a core material in sandwich panel structures to resist loads in different directions. The geometry of the honeycomb core has been used in various fields, including architecture, automotive, aerospace, packaging, medical implants, military industries, and other industries that demand strong and lightweight materials²⁸. Various techniques have been utilized to manufacture biomimetic structures, particularly honeycomb structures. One of the most advanced methods is additive manufacture (AM), commonly referred to three-dimensional (3D) printing, which produce a physical part from a 3D digital model, by laying down and bonding many successive thin layers of material²⁹. A main benefit of this method is its capability to produce parts with complex designs, allowing to produce useful objects, including biomimetic structures, that cannot be easily produced by traditional manufacturing methods³⁰. Various 3D printing methods, such as fused filament fabrication (FFF) or fused deposition modelling (FDM), stereolithography (SLA), laminated object manufacturing (LOM), selective laser melting (SLM), digital light processing (DLP), multijet/polyjet 3D printing, and selective laser sintering (SLS) are available based on the kind of material being used. These techniques utilize distinct materials, including liquids, powders, metals, plastics and sheet-based composite materials³¹.

The most commonly used technique in studies regarding the honeycomb structure is FFF, which creates intricate 3D objects using thermoplastic polymers. Melted filaments of thermoplastic are pulled out onto a solid platform in a semi-solid condition via a heated nozzle throughout the manufacturing process. The parts to be printed are governed by various material and machine parameters^{32,33}. Polylactic acid (PLA), polycarbonate (PC), and Acrylonitrile butadiene styrene (ABS), which have slightly low degrees of melting, are the thermoplastic polymers most frequently utilized in FFF³⁴. Besides these materials, FFF filaments can also be produced from waste or recycled polymers^{35,36}. However, their mechanical characteristics are poor compared to those of virgin materials. Additionally, to address this limitation and improve the mechanical properties of these materials, researchers have explored composite materials for FFF-based applications^{37,38}. Further, parameters affecting FFF-3D printed parts include nozzle temperature, nozzle diameter, platform temperature, air gap, raster angle, print speed, layer thickness, layer resolution, and build orientation³³. Recent studies that have manufactured and evaluated honeycomb structures using FFF technology are as follows. One study investigated the mechanical strength of a honeycomb cellular structure with trabecular bone printed using ABS⁴. The researchers concluded that honeycomb structure is more suitable for applications requiring high strength and toughness properties. However, there was

limited information regarding the printing parameters used and their effects.

In a different study conducted by Bru et al.⁶, three distinct cellular structure configurations (honeycomb, enamel, and bamboo) were evaluated for their compatibility as core materials in sandwich panels. Those structures were printed using PLA material with the following printing parameters: a printing temperature of 210°C, a layer thickness of 0.15 mm, a platform temperature of 80°C, and print speeds of 40 mm/s and 30 mm/s. Their research found that the flexural and compressive properties of the sandwich panels were influenced by core geometry, cell thickness distribution, and relative density.

A similar approach was employed to compare the honeycomb structure with diamond-shaped and corrugated structures printed using a mixture of PLA and Polyhydroxyalkanoate (PHA)⁷. The 3D printing parameters utilized were set at 50 mm/s of a print speed, 0.15 mm of a layer height, 100% of an infill density, 200°C of an extruder temperature, and 60°C of a platform temperature. The findings of this investigation indicated that the structure of the honeycomb yielded the lowest mechanical behavior. Similarly, an evaluation of the mechanical behavior of rhombus and honeycomb structures made with PLA filaments was carried out⁵. The printing parameters employed include an infill density of 100%, a layer thickness of 0.2 mm, a print speed of 60 mm/s, a printing temperature 210°C and a platform temperature of 60°C. The findings indicated that the structure of the honeycomb has poor mechanical behavior. Additionally, the mechanical behavior of a novel honeycomb structural design—more precisely, an octagonal honeycomb, was evaluated experimentally, theoretically, and numerically². Honeycomb structures with different wall thicknesses printed from PLA material were subjected to compression tests. The findings demonstrated that the yield stress and elastic modulus values of the octagonal-shaped honeycomb were comparable to those of the hexagonal (regular) honeycomb. In the same way, a prior study examined how varying the thicknesses of the wall and printing speeds affected the strength of the bonds between layers in PLA and ABS-printed honeycomb core structure³⁹. The results demonstrated that thicker walls had a lower yield point than thinner walls and were more susceptible to plastic deformation. However, both studies did not provide information about the printing parameters used.

Unlike the two previous studies, Yan et al.⁹ focused on improving the mechanical behavior of honeycomb structures by incorporating polymethacrylimide (PMI) absorbent foam within the honeycomb structure. Compression tests were performed on PLA-printed specimens both out-of-plane and in-plane. The outcomes indicated that constructing the honeycomb with absorbent foam resulted in a significant increase in compression

performance compared to an empty honeycomb.

Another study investigated the bending strength of the honeycomb-core sandwich panels printed using varying ratios of PLA and ABS for the core and face/skin materials¹⁰. The printing parameters included a nozzle temperature of 230°C and 250°C, while the platform temperatures were set at 40°C for PLA and 80 °C for ABS materials. The findings indicated that the highest mechanical properties were observed in specimens with a PLA core and face sheet, which were printed using a single extruder assembly.

Meanwhile, Antony et al.¹¹ evaluated the mechanical behavior of honeycomb sandwich structures printed using composite materials (PLA + hemp 20-25%). The purpose of the research was to employ composite materials to enhance the mechanical behavior of the structure. Tensile behavior of hemp fiber/PLA filament-printed specimens with infill angles of 0°/90° and -45°/+45° were analysed. The printing parameters included an extruder temperature of 180°C, bed temperature of 55°C, printing speed of 20 mm/s, 100% infill density, and a layer height of 0.2 mm. The results indicated that specimens printed with an infill angle of 0°/90° showed an increased modulus and tensile strength. Furthermore, a honeycomb core was printed and tested based on ASTM C364 for edgewise compression and ASTM C365 for flatwise compression. They concluded that, compared to flexural properties, the structure demonstrated better compressive strength. The findings also showed that the compressive strength for flatwise specimens was higher than values reported in the literature.

With a similar focus as previous studies, Gohar et al.¹² examined the impact of raster angle variations on the geometry of the face sheet and the combination of materials used in the core and face of the honeycomb-core sandwich panels. They investigated mechanical properties, including flexural strength, edge compressive strength, and interfacial bond strength, of honeycomb-core sandwich panels printed using various materials such as ABS, composite (PLA + 15% carbon fiber), PLA and thermoplastic polyurethane (TPU). The printing parameters applied included 100% infill density, a print speed of 30 mm/s, and a layer height of 0.5 mm. Platform temperatures were set at 80-90°C for ABS, and 50°C for PLA, TPU, and the composite material, with nozzle temperatures at 240-250°C for ABS, 190-200°C for PLA, 220-230°C for TPU, and 190-210°C for composite material. The findings showed that the honeycomb-core sandwich panel's load-bearing capacity is influenced by both the raster angle and material selection. For optimal results, they suggested use ABS for the core and composite for the face sheet, with a raster angle of 0° to 90°.

FFF 3D-printed parts have limitations, such as rough surfaces, low accuracy and precision, and reduced mechanical properties influenced by parameter settings.

Based on the literature reviewed above, considerable effort has been made to improve and investigate various factors affecting the mechanical behavior of honeycomb-shaped structure and their application as sandwich panel core-structures. These efforts include optimizing the range of printing parameters particularly, such as print speed⁸, raster layup¹², and infill angle¹¹. However, parameters in the FFF technique have yet to be optimized alongside other factors affecting the mechanical properties of honeycomb structures applied as sandwich panel core-structure. Therefore, to fill the research gap, this study will focus on optimizing 3D printing parameters (e.g., print speed, layer height, nozzle temperature, and platform temperature) to enhance the mechanical behavior of the honeycomb-bioinspired structure, applied as sandwich panel core-structure and evaluate the significant impact of these printing parameters on the mechanical behavior of the honeycomb core-sandwich panel. A key distinction of this study from prior works lies in the broader range and number of parameters and levels considered, as well as the optimization method employed.

2. Material and Methods

The material utilized in this research was PLA Plus filament, a thermoplastic polymer that is biodegradable and made from renewable materials, including sugarcane, cassava, and maize starch^{40,41}. PLA filament with a 0.75 mm diameter (eSUN PLA Plus brand) was purchased from 3D Zaiku Indonesia to print the specimens. The additive manufacturing technique employed was FFF 3D printer type Haltech H-02.

In the present study, we identified printing parameters influencing the characteristic of the honeycomb-core sandwich panel. These parameters such as print speed, layer height, nozzle temperature, and platform temperature are selected based on the parameters set in the previous studies. The three levels of each parameter were determined to encompass the range of values reported in the previous studies. The first level of the nozzle temperature was adopted from Antony et al.¹¹, the middle level was selected from Bru et al.⁶ and Faidallah et al.⁵, while the highest level was derived from Brischetto et al.¹⁰. For the layer height, the lowest level was taken from Brischetto et al.¹⁰, whereas the highest level was based on the work of Gohar et al.¹². The intermediate level was determined by calculating the median value between the first and third levels. Regarding print speed, the lowest level was referenced from Antony et al.¹¹, the middle level from Bru et al.⁶, and the highest level from Faidallah et al.⁵. Lastly, the platform temperature levels were established with the first level derived from Brischetto et al.¹⁰, the second from Faidallah et al.⁵, and the third from Bru et al.⁶

The parameters and levels selected were then designed into

design of experiments (DOE) framework, utilizing the Taguchi method as an optimization method which has the advantage of requiring fewer experimental combinations, making it more efficient than traditional design methods⁴²⁾ and resulting robust design of an experiment. An L9 Orthogonal Array (OA) was used to arrange a combination of three levels across four parameters or factors, producing a balanced series of experiments. The selected levels and parameters are presented in Table 1, while Table 2 depicts the L9 OA setup used in this study.

Table 1: Parameter and level selection

Process parameters	Levels			Units
	1	2	3	
Nozzle Temperature	180	210	230	°C
Layer Height	0.1	0.3	0.5	mm
Print Speed	20	40	60	mm/s
Platform Temperature	40	60	80	°C

Table 2: The L9 orthogonal arra

Run	Nozzle Temperature	Layer Height	Print Speed	Platform Temperature
1	1	1	1	1
2	1	2	2	2
3	1	3	3	3
4	2	1	2	3
5	2	2	3	1
6	2	3	1	2
7	3	1	3	2
8	3	2	1	3
9	3	3	2	1

After that, the digital 3D design that has been created using Solidwork 2018 software was used to print the tested specimen. The dimensions of the honeycomb-core sandwich panel specimens were designed according to ASTM C365⁴³⁾ for compression tests and ASTM C393⁴⁴⁾ for bending tests as depicted in Figure 1.

The 3D file then transformed into a stereolithography (STL) file format and sliced using Ultimaker Cura 3.6.0 software. Slicing settings were determined based on the combination of parameters and levels specified in L9 array. The resulting G-code file was transferred to the FFF printer, which printed the specimens as shown in Figure 2. There were fifty-four samples printed in all, with three reprints for each of the nine compression and bending test runs.

Furthermore, the mechanical behaviors of the specimens were evaluated using a CRN-50 Universal Testing Machine (UTM) in accordance with ASTM C365 and ASTM C393 standards, as illustrated in Figure 3. The compression test was conducted at a crosshead speed of 0.5 mm/s, while the bending test was performed at a speed of 6 mm/s. The span length applied in the bending test was 100 mm. The specimens were compressed until they failed to determine the maximum load capacity. The experimental data obtained were subsequently used to

calculate the compressive and flexural strengths of the honeycomb-core sandwich panel specimens. The compressive strength (σ_c) and bending strength (σ_b) were calculated using equations (1) and (2).

$$\sigma_c = P_c/A_c \tag{1}$$

$$\sigma_b = 3PS/2bd^2 \tag{2}$$

Fig. 1: Dimensions and structure of specimens (a) Compression test; (b) Bending Test

Fig. 2: The manufacturing process: (a) Specimen printing for compression test (b) Specimen printing for three-point bending test

Fig. 3: Specimens testing: (a) compression (b) three-point bending

Where P_c stands for the ultimate load during the compression test of the specimens (N), and A_c denotes the cross-sectional area of the sandwich specimens (mm^2). Additionally, P refers to the force (N) at a particular location on the load-deflection curve of the bending test, S is the length of the support span (mm), while b represents the width (mm) and d refers to the thickness (mm) of the sandwich specimen.

The data were analysed using “larger the better” type Signal to Noise Ratio (SNR) to determine the optimal values of the parameters used. The optimal value of each parameter was determined based on the highest SNR at each level of the parameters. Meanwhile, the delta value was calculated to indicate the order or rank of the parameter’s influence on the variation in the process results. Then, a statistical analysis, Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), was performed to evaluate the significant impact of the parameters on the mechanical properties of the specimens. Minitab 18 software was utilized in this stage. Finally, the conclusions were made based on the results of the analysis.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Compression Test

The compression test results, as summarized in Table 3, indicate that the specimen can withstand a maximum load of 4.69 kN, with the highest compressive strength recorded at 1.88 MPa. Both of these values were obtained from specimen 4. Furthermore, the data were analyzed using the Taguchi method in Minitab software.

Table 3: Compression test results

Run	Experimental results	
	Average Maximum Load (kN)	Average Compressive strength (MPa)
1	4.376	1.75
2	3.807	1.52
3	2.041	0.82
4	4.692	1.88
5	3.427	1.37
6	3.801	1.52
7	3.582	1.43
8	4.672	1.87
9	3.713	1.49

This study aims to identify optimal variations in parameters that yield the best mechanical properties (compressive strength) of the honeycomb-core sandwich panel specimens. The data were analyzed using the “larger is better” SNR response, as higher mechanical strength is preferable. The parameter with the most influence is identified by calculating the highest delta, which represents the range between the highest and lowest values of the Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR) at each level.

Figure 4 presents the outcomes of the Taguchi analysis

conducted on the compressive strength data. The parameters that have the most effect on the compressive strength are print speed, followed by layer height and nozzle temperature. Conversely, platform temperature has the least impact on compressive strength.

Fig. 4: The SNR of the parameter effect on compressive strength

Changes in each parameter level affect the compressive strength values. As the nozzle temperature improves, the compressive strength of the specimen also increases; however, only a slight increase is observed when it reaches a temperature of 230°C. Additionally, lower layer heights, print speeds, and platform temperatures contribute to higher compressive strength values. Further, the optimal parameter settings are determined based on the highest SNR value at each parameter level. Therefore, the optimal level of parameter settings identified are 230°C nozzle temperature, 0.1 mm layer height, 20 mm/s print speed, and 40°C platform temperature.

Furthermore, a General Linear Model ANOVA, which is an extension of the regression model to assess the effect of each parameter, was performed using Minitab software in this study. The calculations determined each p-value and sum of square (SS), which serve as the basis for evaluating significant effects and a percentage of contributions of each parameter to the results. The null hypothesis (H_0) used is the printing parameters insignificantly influence the mechanical properties of the honeycomb core-sandwich panels. A 5% significance level (α) was applied, and if the p-value is less than 0.05 or the F-value ($F_{2,18}=3.55$) is greater than the F-table, the null hypothesis (H_0) would be rejected.

The ANOVA results for the compressive strength data, shown in Table 4, show that the compressive strength of the honeycomb-core sandwich panel specimens was significantly affected by nozzle temperature, layer height, and print speed. It was supported by the p-values less than 0.05. In contrast, platform temperature does not have a significant effect, supported by the p-value greater than 0.05, indicating that at whatever level this parameter is set, the effect given has no significant change in the

compressive strength property. Print speed contributes the most, accounting for 44.7% of the variance, while nozzle temperature contributes the least, at 10.7%. However,

there is still 16.1% variance contributed by other factors that were not considered or controlled in this study.

Table 4: ANOVA on Compressive Strength

Source	DF	Adj-SS	Adj-MS	F-Value	P-Value	Contribution (%)
Nozzle Temperature	2	0.32	0.16	5.95	0.01	10.7
Layer Height	2	0.84	0.42	15.74	<0.0001	28.2
Print Speed	2	1.32	0.66	24.96	<0.0001	44.7
Platform Temperature	2	0.01	0.004	0.16	0.85	0.3
Error	18	0.48	0.03			16.1
Total	26	2.96				100

3.2. Bending Test

The bending test outcomes in Table 5 depict that the maximum load the specimen can withstand is 0.28 kN, with the highest flexural strength of 9.4 MPa, both recorded for specimen 1. Additionally, the data were analyzed to determine the SNR value at each parameter level.

Table 5: Bending test results

Run	Experimental results	
	Average Maximum Load (kN)	Average Bending strength (MPa)
1	0.282	9.40
2	0.228	7.60
3	0.048	1.60
4	0.271	9.04
5	0.24	7.96
6	0.239	7.69
7	0.234	7.80
8	0.276	9.20
9	0.231	7.71

Figure 5 presents the SNR plot for each parameter level, indicating that the most important factor influencing flexural strength is layer height, then followed by print speed, nozzle and platform temperature. Conversely, platform temperature exhibits the least influence on the bending strength of the honeycomb-core sandwich panel specimens.

Results indicate that increasing the nozzle temperature enhances flexural strength; however, the effect becomes insignificant at 230°C. Conversely, flexural strength

increases as print speed, layer height, and platform temperature decrease. Therefore, the optimal parameter values for maximizing flexural strength in the honeycomb-core sandwich panel are a nozzle temperature of 230 °C, a layer height of 0.1 mm, a printing speed of 20 mm/s, and a platform temperature of 40°C.

The ANOVA test results in Table 6 show that the p-values were less than 0.05, indicating that nozzle temperature, layer height, print speed, and platform temperature significantly affect the flexural strength of the honeycomb-core sandwich panel specimens. It means that these printing parameters are very important to consider in this case. Of these, layer height contributes the most, with a contribution of 35.8%, while platform temperature contributes the least, at 10.1%. Additionally, other factors not included in this study only contributed approximately 4%.

Figure 5: The SNR of the parameter effect on bending strength

Table 6: ANOVA on Bending Strength

Source	DF	Adj-SS	Adj-MS	F-Value	P-Value	Contribution (%)
Nozzle Temperature	2	24,81	124,04	41,09	<0.0001	18.03
Layer Height	2	49,28	246,38	81,61	<0.0001	35.81
Print Speed	2	44,18	220,9	73,17	<0.0001	32.11
Platform Temperature	2	13,9	69,52	23,03	<0.0001	10.10
Error	18	5,43	0,30			3.95
Total	26	137,6				100

3.3. An Analysis of Parameters Effect

The compression test results on all specimens indicate that the print speed parameter has the most substantial impact compared to the other three parameters. The highest compression and bending test values were achieved at slower print speeds (20 mm/s). Reducing print speed enhances both compressive strength and bending strength due to the increased bonding time between layers, reducing porosity and fracture occurrence in the printed object⁴⁵⁾. Applying high print speeds can lead to defects in the specimen, often caused by insufficient material flow over the printed layers⁴⁶⁾.

The nozzle temperature is an essential parameter in regulating the fluidity of the deposited material during the printing process of 3D parts. When the nozzle temperature is too low, the extruded material lacks sufficient fluidity, which prevents proper adhesion to the previously deposited layers and can lead to poor molding quality. On the other hand, excessively high nozzle temperatures can cause the material to become overly liquid or even undergo minor thermal degradation, negatively affecting the final quality of the printed structure^{47,48)}. Finding the optimal nozzle temperature is critical for enhancing the mechanical behavior of printed components. At a nozzle temperature of 180°C, compressive strength decreases due to insufficient fluidity and weak interlayer bonding. Increasing the nozzle temperature to 210°C significantly improves both compressive and flexural strengths, attributed to better flow and stronger interlayer adhesion. At 230°C, we observed a small increase in compressive and flexural strength values.

In FFF, the platform temperature plays a role for enhancing material strength by maintaining the printed object's temperature above the temperature of glass transition (T_g) and allowing it to cool gradually. This process, known as annealing, aims to strengthen the material by promoting crystallinity in the polymer, which directly correlates with increased material strength. Experimental findings reveal that a decrease in the platform temperature to 40°C contributes to improved compressive and flexural strength values. Lower platform temperatures likely facilitate more gradual cooling, which may encourage crystalline formation, thus enhancing the mechanical behavior of the 3D printed structure.

Additionally, during the compression and bending test, the load is distributed between the fiber strength and the interlayer bonding (cohesion) within the specimen. Compression and bending strength improve when interlayer bonding is stronger or when the layer height is reduced. However, reducing the layer height increases the quantity of layers needed to finish the printing process, leading to longer printing times for the specimen.⁴⁰⁾

3.4. A comparative analysis of the mechanical behavior of honeycomb structures

In this study, the mechanical properties of the honeycomb structure core were calculated. When compared to research conducted by Yoon et al⁴⁾, the mechanical strength achieved through parameter optimization remains below 83.7% of the compressive stress value produced by the honeycomb structure with dimensions $l \times b \times h$ (30.38 mm \times 30.61 mm \times 30.23 mm). Additionally, variations in specimen sizes and the use of different filaments, including ABS, contribute to the differences in compressive strength values observed.

In the tests conducted by Bru et al.⁶⁾, the maximum loads achieved in the compression and bending tests were 212.8% and 12.8% lower than the maximum loads supported by the optimized specimen in this study. Additionally, the inclusion of foam in the honeycomb structure led to a 23.47% increase in compressive strength, as reported by Yan et al.⁹⁾, which surpasses the results found in the current study. While the flexural strength obtained here remains below 80% of the values reported by Brischetto et al.¹⁰⁾; however, this study demonstrates superior performance regarding the average maximum load the specimen can withstand. Notably, specimen dimensions, particularly width and thickness, significantly influence the observed differences in results. Furthermore, variations in cell size, face/skin thickness, and the combination of materials used (such as hemp and PLA) in their study contribute to the differences compared to the findings of the current research.

The outcomes of this research indicate a bending strength value that is 57% lower than that of specimens consisting of a face sheet and core printed with a 0°/90° raster angle using composite and ABS, but represents a 135% increase compared to the specimen consisting of a TPU core and PLA face sheets printed with a 45°/-45° raster angle, as reported by Gohar et al¹²⁾. In comparison with a study reported by Zaharia et al.⁷⁾, this research achieved increases in compressive strength and bending strength of 17% and 7%, respectively. In contrast, the findings of Faidallah et al.⁵⁾ indicated that this study was able to enhance flexural strength by 34%. However, compressive strength remained below 60%.

In conclusion, Table 7 provides a comparison of the optimization results with those of previous studies that employed the same dimensional specifications and specimen sizes.

Table 7: Comparison of research results

Research sources	Compressive Strength (MPa)	Flexural Strength (MPa)
Zaharia et al. ⁷⁾	1.6	8.8
Faidallah et al. ⁵⁾	4.69	7
Current research	1.88	9.4

4. Conclusion

This study optimized the process parameters of the FFF printing process to enhance the mechanical behavior of honeycomb-core sandwich panels and evaluated the significance of these parameters. The Taguchi method was employed to determine the optimal parameter settings for compressive and flexural tests. The results indicate that the optimal combination of parameters—230°C nozzle temperature, 0.1 mm layer height, 20 mm/s print speed, and 40°C platform temperature—yielded the highest compressive and flexural strengths of 1.88 MPa and 9.4 MPa, respectively. This finding in general had higher values of mechanical properties of the honeycomb-core sandwich panel compared to the previous studies which utilized similar dimensional specifications and specimen sizes. ANOVA analysis revealed that nozzle temperature, layer height, and print speed significantly influence compressive strength, while platform temperature has an insignificant effect. In contrast, all parameters significantly impact flexural strength. Future studies could extend this research by exploring additional factors, such as variations in honeycomb topology, sandwich panel surface thickness, and different material compositions, to further optimize the mechanical properties of these structures.

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Nomenclature

%	Percentage
α	Alpha
σ_b	Bending strength
σ_c	Compressive strength
°C	degrees Celsius
3D	Three dimensional
ABS	Acetonitrile butadiene styrene
AM	Additive manufacture
ANOVA	Analysis of Variance
ASTM	American Society for testing and materials
DF	Degree of Freedom
DLP	Digital light processing
DOE	Design of experiment
FDM	Fused deposition modelling
FFF	Fused filament fabrication
F-value	Fisher value
H_0	Null hypothesis
kN	kilonewton
LOM	Laminated object manufacturing
N	Newton
mm/s	Millimeter per second
MPa	Megapascal
MS	Mean square

OA	Orthogonal array
PHA	Polyhydroxyalkanoate
PLA	Poly lactide acid
PMI	Polymethacrylimide
P-value	Probability value
SLA	Stereolithography
SLM	Selective laser melting
SNR	Signal-to-noise ratio
SS	Sum of square
T _g	Glass transition temperature
TPU	Thermoplastic polyurethane
UTM	Universal testing machine

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